

Mapping the Habitation Patterns and Socio-ecological Dynamics of Kittiwakes along the River Tyne

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Abstract

The project, funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC, #UKRI271), explores the socio-ecological dynamics of urban kittiwakes along the River Tyne, highlighting their unique integration into the urban environments of Newcastle and Gateshead, UK. Since their initial settlement on industrial riverside structures in the 1960s, these unique seabirds have expanded to occupy a range of urban sites, including the Tyne Bridge and the Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art (Coulson, 2019; Turner, 2010, 2020). While celebrated by many, their presence has also led to tensions over noise and waste, prompting the use of deterrent measures to prevent them from landing and nesting on man-made structures (Turner, 2002; Newcastle City Council, 2019; Wilson, 2022). Adopting a "more-than-human" perspective, this research integrates ethnographic methods, GIS mapping, and machine learning approaches to examine kittiwake habitats and spatial interactions. Through analysis of multi-source datasets (2010-2025), the random forest model revealed the most influential environmental predictors of kittiwake presence, while GIS-based spatial analysis revealed the dominant urban morphological factors influencing habitat selection, with colonies exploiting diverse neighbourhood structures along the riverfront. The analysis also identified multiple breeding hotspots extending beyond iconic structures, revealing successful urban adaptation supported by cliff-analogue architectural features and navigable flight corridors to marine foraging areas. The findings demonstrate that kittiwakes' urban presence is influenced by specific aspects of urban morphology rather than coastal proximity alone, providing insights for developing inclusive urban planning strategies that foster sustainable multispecies coexistence.

Keywords: urban ecology, geographical information systems, machine learning, more-than-human, kittiwake

Introduction

Contemporary urban studies increasingly recognise that cities are not exclusively human constructs but complex socio-ecological assemblages where multiple species actively shape urban development trajectories (Alberti, 2008 & 2010; Wilson, 2022). However, mainstream urban theory continues to privilege human agency, treating non-human urban inhabitants as passive recipients of anthropogenic environments rather than active participants in urban morphological processes (Hassell et al., 2020). This shapes our understanding of how cities function and who can legitimately claim urban space. The phenomenon is especially apparent in the colonisation patterns of urban-adapted wildlife, whose habitat choices expose the morphological features and evolutionary trajectories underpinning urban environments (Decandia et al., 2019). The River Tyne corridor

between Newcastle and Gateshead, UK, provides an exceptional case study for understanding these dynamics through the lens of black-legged kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*)—seabirds that have undergone a remarkable urban transition since the 1960s (Coulson, 2019; Turner, 2010, 2020).

The Tyne Valley's urban morphology reflects centuries of industrial evolution, from medieval settlement patterns to Victorian industrial expansion and contemporary post-industrial regeneration (Barke, 2022; Jin et al., 2025). This morphological layering has created a unique architectural ecology characterised by riverside industrial heritage that inadvertently replicates the coastal cliff environments favoured by kittiwakes in their natural habitats (Turner, 2010). The birds' selective occupation of specific urban structures, including the iconic Tyne Bridge, the Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art, and various riverside buildings, reveals critical insights into how urban form influences 'multispecies cohabitation' (Roudavski, 2020). The kittiwakes' urban adaptation strategy demonstrates sophisticated responses to morphological features such as height above ground, building material and surface texture, narrow ledges, and proximity to water sources (Turner 2020; Stone, 2025). Their preference for industrial-era architecture over contemporary glass facades suggests that certain morphological elements facilitate ecological integration, while others present barriers. This selective colonisation pattern illuminates how historical urban development processes continue to influence contemporary ecological relationships, creating what might be termed "morphological affordances" for non-human urban inhabitants.

Although research on urban gulls and kittiwake ecology is expanding (Turner, 2010; Dalla Pria et al., 2022; Wilson, 2022; Langley et al., 2023; Goumas et al., 2024), studies integrating advanced spatial analysis and machine learning with more-than-human theoretical frameworks to understand kittiwake-urban morphology relationships remain limited. Addressing this gap could yield finer-scale insights into the factors shaping habitat-use behaviours and provide data-led recommendations for incorporating urban environments into conservation strategies. This investigation addresses three interconnected research questions that link avian ecology with urban morphological analysis: 1) How do specific environmental characteristics influence kittiwake habitat selection and colony establishment? 2) In what ways can urban morphological design and built environmental measures contribute to establishing a resilient environment for Tyne kittiwakes? And 3) What implications does this understanding of interspecies urban morphology hold for developing more inclusive urban planning and design practices?

These questions are approached through a "more-than-human" (MTH) framework that conceptualises cities as assemblages of human and non-human actors, where urban form evolves through ongoing interspecies negotiations rather than exclusively anthropocentric planning (Rupprecht et al., 2017). Methodologically, it integrates ethnographic observation with advanced spatial analysis and AI techniques to document kittiwake nesting sites, population densities, and colonisation patterns alongside fine-grained urban morphological data. This combined approach uncovers correlations between ecological habitat preferences and urban form, offering new analytical tools for planners to anticipate how proposed developments may shape multispecies urban dynamics. Beyond methodological innovation, the research invites residents and policymakers to embrace the MTH perspective, transforming how public space, urban belonging, and water-based infrastructures are conceived and managed.

Theoretical Framework: A More-than-human Approach

This research is grounded in a MTH theoretical framework that challenges anthropocentric understandings of urban space and morphological development (Rautio, 2013). Drawing from posthumanist geography and multispecies studies, this approach recognises cities not as exclusively human constructs but as dynamic assemblages where human and non-human actors continuously co-produce urban environments through ongoing negotiations, adaptations, and spatial practices (Hinchliffe & Whatmore; 2006 Whatmore, 2017). The MTH perspective provides a crucial lens for understanding how kittiwakes actively shape urban morphology, and it also guided the design of

participatory workshops for 'Navigating Urban Ecologies', enabling local communities to collaboratively explore and engage with interspecies urban dynamics.

Traditional urban morphology research has predominantly focused on human agency in shaping urban form, treating non-human species as passive occupants of anthropogenic environments. The MTH approach disrupts this anthropocentric bias by acknowledging that cities are fundamentally interspecies spaces where various actors possess agency in shaping urban development (Latour, 2005). In the case of Tyne kittiwakes, this theoretical lens reveals how these seabirds function not merely as ecological inhabitants but as active urban agents. The framework draws particularly on Actor-Network Theory (ANT) to understand how kittiwakes become enrolled in urban assemblages, forming hybrid networks that include architectural structures, environmental conditions, human communities, and policy frameworks (Hinchliffe, 2007). These networks are not static but continuously reconfigured through the dynamic interactions between human and non-human actors, creating what Whatmore (2017) terms "hybrid geographies", where the boundaries between nature and culture become increasingly blurred. The kittiwakes' occupation of prominent architectural structures like the Tyne Bridge and Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art represent more than ecological adaptation; they constitute active spatial claiming that challenges anthropocentric assumptions about urban belonging.

Interspecies cohabitation also moves beyond traditional human–wildlife conflict paradigms toward more nuanced understandings of shared urban space (Buller, 2014; McInturff et al., 2025). Over decades, the urban presence of kittiwakes in Newcastle and Gateshead has generated tensions within the built environment: nesting behaviour produces acoustic disturbances, organic waste, and maintenance challenges, prompting property owners and municipal authorities to deploy deterrent technologies such as physical barriers and avishock devices. Rather than viewing kittiwakes as invasive species requiring management, MTH framework positions them as legitimate urban residents with spatial claims that can be 'negotiated' alongside human interests (Roudavski, 2020). This perspective aligns with emerging calls for multispecies urban planning that recognises the rights and needs of non-human inhabitants (Ferraz et al., 2025). Expanding Lefebvre's (1968) "right to the city" through a posthumanist critique, the MTH approach conceives urban space as constituted through ongoing negotiations among multiple species, each with legitimate claims to inhabit and shape the city (Wolch, 2002).

Importantly, the framework incorporates temporal dimensions, recognising that urban assemblages are processes of continuous becoming rather than static entities (Massey, 2005). The sixty-year history of kittiwake urban colonisation along the Tyne demonstrates how interspecies relationships evolve through time, creating new urban morphological possibilities while foreclosing others. This temporal perspective reveals how current urban forms carry traces of past interspecies negotiations while remaining open to future transformations through ongoing interspecies encounters. By adopting this theoretical framework, the research contributes to growing scholarship on posthumanist urban studies while providing practical insights for developing more inclusive approaches to urban morphology that acknowledge the agency and spatial claims of non-human urban inhabitants.

Methodology

Study Area

This study is based in North East England, focusing on the twin cities of Newcastle and Gateshead (Figure 1). These urban centres have historically developed around the River Tyne, whose industrial and economic significance has long shaped the region's identity and growth. The tidal estuary of the River Tyne is a vital feature for understanding the urban ecology of seabirds (Turner, 2010). Kittiwake breeding colonies have extended up to 24 kilometres inland, with significant numbers now occupying riverside buildings in both Newcastle and Gateshead, marking a notable inland shift in their nesting behaviour (Coulson, 2011). The River Tyne offers a unique urban geography directly linked to the

sea, an essential condition for urban nesting seabirds (Redfern & Bevan, 2014). This coastal-urban continuum has enabled kittiwakes to adapt successfully to a diverse range of urban structures, including warehouses, piers, bridges, and even artificial nesting towers.

Figure 1. Case study context, the bottom right image is sourced from Turner, D. M., *River Tyne Black-legged Kittiwake (*Rissa tridactyla*) Colonies on Man-Made Structures, 1994–2009*.

Data and Analysis

Records of kittiwakes in the study area derive from multiple sources, with the earliest data dating back to 1938. As urban-nesting populations expanded, monitoring sources diversified to include both volunteer citizen scientists and professional ornithologists. However, existing sources varied considerably in spatial precision and temporal coverage, with some records lacking geocoded locations or detailed abundance counts, and data quality differing between volunteer observations and systematic professional surveys.

To illustrate this variability, the Baltic Flour Mill, which became the primary focus of kittiwake activity on the Tyne by the 1990s, has been recognised as a key observational site. Following the mill's redevelopment into the Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art (opened 2002), the site has been monitored regularly by local ornithologists including Daniel Turner and supported by Durham Wildlife Trust's kittiwake camera initiative (Durham Wildlife Trust, 2025). Surveys at this site are conducted annually from April to July at intervals ranging from two to ten days to document temporal changes in abundance throughout the nesting season, providing high-resolution temporal data with precise spatial coordinates. Meanwhile, the British Trust for Ornithology (BTO) dataset encompasses observations from 192 additional locations across the broader study region. These data are

contributed by trained citizen scientists capable of reliably distinguishing *Rissa tridactyla* from morphologically similar seabird species through established BTO identification protocols.

To map and analyse the presence and distribution of Tyne kittiwakes within the case study area, three primary datasets were selected, cleaned, and integrated based on their complementary strengths:

- (i) BirdTrack (<https://www.bto.org/our-science/projects/birdtrack>)
- (ii) BTO Atlas (<https://www.bto.org/our-science/projects/birdtrack-store/taking-part/birdtrack-lists-and-bto-atlases>)
- (iii) ERIC Northeast (Environmental Records Information Centre; <https://ericnortheast.org.uk/eric-data-information/>),

Together, these datasets offer complementary spatial and temporal coverage, balancing the broad geographic scope of citizen science observations with the rigour of systematic monitoring programmes and regional biodiversity documentation. Accordingly, a comprehensive data-cleaning process was undertaken, including manual verification and geocoding. The analysis focused on the period 2010–2025, reflecting the period of substantial population growth when colony size approximately doubled (Turner, 2010).

While existing ornithological studies predominantly emphasise micro-scale architectural features of individual nesting sites, significant quantitative gaps remain in explicitly linking broader urban morphological metrics, such as land cover and land use, to kittiwake abundance and distribution dynamics (Xue et al., 2020; Dalla Pria et al., 2022; Spelt et al., 2019). This study addresses these critical knowledge gaps by integrating ecological habitat modelling with urban morphological analysis through two complementary analytical approaches: Machine Learning (ML) to identify macro-level environmental drivers influencing kittiwake urban inhabitation, while GIS-based spatial analysis examined how built environment characteristics and land use configurations shape patterns of kittiwake abundance, colony distribution, and population persistence within the city. This dual-method approach enabled a comprehensive assessment spanning from broad environmental factors to fine-grained morphological characteristics, revealing critical thresholds and spatial patterns influencing urban colonisation success.

By examining how environmental and morphological factors collectively shape kittiwake urban inhabitation patterns and population dynamics, the analysis generated insights into the spatial conditions and habitat configurations that support the long-term resilience and successful establishment of the Tyne kittiwake colony.

Environmental Predictors of Kittiwake Presence

To characterise the urban habitat, spatial layers were generated based on land use, land cover, and building structure data obtained from the UKCEH Land Cover Maps (UKCEH, 2023; Morton et al., 2024). Proximity to environmental features, including freshwater bodies, saltwater bodies, urban and suburban areas, and green spaces was calculated using the Euclidean Distance tool within the Spatial Analyst extension of SciPy (version 1.15.3) and ScikitLearn (version 1.7.0). Each predictor variable represents a hypothesis collectively tested to explain the presence and distribution of Kittiwakes across the study area. Following the computation of all predictor variables and their integration with kittiwake (*Rissa tridactyla*) presence/pseudo-absence survey data, the resulting dataset comprised 5,748 observations (rows) with five corresponding predictor variables (columns). To address the lack of true absence data, a lattice grid vector layer was created with a point spacing

of 500 meters. Pseudo-absence points were then generated by randomly sampling grid cells in which kittiwakes had not been recorded. These pseudo-absences served as surrogate representations of true absences, thereby enabling presence–absence modelling.

The primary objective of the modelling was not to predict kittiwake presence per se, but to identify the environmental features influencing their urban habitat selection. As such, the analysis emphasised the interpretation of feature importance rather than predictive accuracy.

Following pseudo-absence generation, the dataset was temporally partitioned into training and testing subsets. The training set included data from 2010 to 2019, while the testing set comprised data from 2020 to 2024. This temporal split was designed to ensure that the test data aligned with the most up-to-date land cover dataset, minimising the impact of outdated structural information and allowing for a more accurate assessment of contemporary habitat influences on kittiwake distribution. A set of established Machine Learning (ML) algorithms was tested, including leading approaches identified in previous studies (Hegel et al., 2010; Fernández-Delgado et al., 2014) for an overview. Among these, the Random Forest predictor was found to achieve the highest ROC (receiving operator characteristic) curve scores, a metric used to evaluate the performance of a binary classification model. The specific algorithms and their parameter settings are described below. In addition, it also has robustness in handling non-linear ecological data, robustness to overfitting, and effectiveness in modelling complex ecological relationships (Breiman, 1999).

The modelling framework was specified as:

Presence/Absence ~ Distance to Fresh Water + Distance to Salt Water + Distance to Urban + Distance to Suburban + Distance to Green

Hyperparameter tuning was performed to optimise model performance. Predictive ability for presence/absence was evaluated on temporally independent test data using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) as the performance metric.

Morphological Factors Influencing Kittiwake Abundance

To investigate how urban morphology influences kittiwake habitat selection, colony establishment, and long-term population resilience, GIS-based spatial analysis was employed to systematically examine colony distribution patterns in relation to key morphological indicators, complementing the machine learning modelling described previously.

Kittiwake abundance data were first categorised according to land use classifications to understand spatial distribution patterns and population dynamics within the study area. The percentage of kittiwake abundance (number of individuals) was calculated for each land cover class using Verisk UKLand (2023) data accessed via Digimap : (1) Green—recreational areas, farmlands, parks, and woodlands; (2) Blue—coastal and inland waters and wetlands; (3) Retail—large shopping complexes, business parks, and urban commercial centres; (4) Mixed-use—high-density residential areas with integrated retail and commercial functions, medium-density buildings with local amenities, and high street locations; (5) Residential—low-density suburban developments; and (6) Vacant—former mining sites, brownfield land, and transport infrastructure including major roads and bridges.

Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) was subsequently applied to visualise emergent geospatial patterns and identify significant concentration hotspots within the urban environment. This geo-visualisation technique contextualised kittiwake abundance by revealing spatial clustering in relation

to specific environmental features and morphological characteristics. The resulting quantitative spatial metrics enabled statistical assessment of habitat preferences and identification of critical environmental thresholds influencing successful urban colonisation and population persistence. By mapping density patterns across different land use categories, the analysis illuminated how particular configurations of urban morphology create differential opportunities for kittiwake establishment and breeding success.

Findings

Environmental Predictors

The Random Forest model demonstrated excellent predictive performance for presence–absence classification, achieving an Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (AUROC) of 0.99 when tested on data collected since 2020 (Figure 2). This high level of accuracy is likely attributable, in part, to the species' strong site fidelity and consistent breeding behaviour, including loyalty to both nesting partners and specific locations (Regan et al., 2024). Feature importance analysis identified distance to saltwater as the most influential environmental predictor, followed by proximity to urban areas. These results indicate that marine access combined with tall urban structures suitable for nesting constitutes the primary determinant of kittiwake habitat selection and colony establishment (Fairweather and Coulson, 1995). Notably, green space—whilst generally recognised as valuable for urban biodiversity—emerged as the least important variable influencing kittiwake presence. This finding aligns with the species' pelagic ecology and specialist foraging behaviour, which depends exclusively on marine prey rather than terrestrial food sources. The predominance of coastal proximity and urban structural characteristics over vegetated areas in the predictive model underscores how kittiwake habitat requirements differ fundamentally from those of most urban wildlife, reflecting their adaptation to exploit specific morphological features of the built environment rather than conventional green infrastructure.

Figure 2. Model evaluation results. (a) Confusion matrix showing model classification performance between presence and absence classes, (b) Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve indicating high predictive accuracy (AUC = 0.99), (c) Top 5 Feature importance ranking

Morphological Factors

This finding is further supported by the distribution of kittiwake abundance across urban land use classes, which indicates that urban kittiwake distribution is less tied to green space availability (Figure 3). The analysis reveals a marked preference for retail buildings, which dominate habitat selection, accounting for over 60% of observations. Urban infrastructure, particularly bridge structures across the river, accounts for approximately 13% of observations, while mixed-use developments represent around 10% of recorded sites.

Figure 3. Distribution of kittiwake abundance by land use classification.

Figures 4(a) and 4(b) illustrate the spatial distribution of observed kittiwake locations and Kernel Density Estimation based on abundance at each site. The mapping reveals concentration patterns along the coastline and the river corridor flowing through central Newcastle and Gateshead. A more detailed KDE analysis focusing on this central area (Figure 5) identifies multiple breeding hotspots distributed across the commercial riverfront, extending beyond well-known structures such as the Tyne Bridge and Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art. This pattern demonstrates that colonies exploit a variety of neighbourhood structures along the riverside, and its spatial distribution reflects successful urban adaptation driven by the confluence of multiple morphological and environmental factors. The central urban corridor provides environmental stability through sheltered microclimates whilst the linear river geography establishes navigable flight corridors enabling efficient access to the North Sea foraging areas. The persistence of industrial-era architectural elements such as vertical surfaces, protruding ledges, and elevated positions creates cliff-analogous morphological features that functionally substitute for natural nesting habitats. Together, these interconnected spatial and morphological characteristics generate viable breeding environments within the metropolitan landscape, enabling kittiwake populations to establish and maintain colonies in contexts typically considered incompatible with seabird ecology.

Figure 4. (a) Observed kittiwake locations, (b) KDE highlighting the spatial distribution of the birds (based on abundance).

Figure 5. KDE kittiwake abundance in central Newcastle/Gateshead.

However, with field recordings and spatial analysis, this study also reveals the tensions inherent in multispecies urban cohabitation. Anthropogenic exclusion measures, particularly extensive vertical netting installations on riverside buildings (Figure 6), create comprehensive year-round deterrent zones to contested urban space. These deterrent measures function as material expressions of competing spatial rights, forcing bird populations to concentrate into fewer accessible sites and potentially intensifying competition at remaining locations.

Figure 6. Full-height vertical netting was installed along the façade and ledges of the Quayside building, preventing kittiwakes and other birds from nesting (source: authors' field photographs).

This dynamic illustrates what Roudavski (2020) describes as “architectural negotiation” wherein built structures become arenas of ongoing contestation between species, each asserting spatial needs and territorial claims. The resulting urban landscape represents neither purely human nor purely avian space, but rather a contested terrain where morphological features simultaneously enable and constrain multispecies cohabitation. The concentration patterns visible in Figure 5 thus map not merely ecological habitat preferences but the spatial outcomes of decades-long interspecies negotiations. It reveals which architectural features have remained accessible and which have been

successfully defended by human interests. From an MTH perspective, these exclusion measures exemplify how urban morphology is continuously reconfigured through interspecies conflict and negotiation rather than existing as a static backdrop to ecological processes. The installation of deterrent devices represents human efforts to reassert control over architectural surfaces. Yet, the persistence of nesting colonies, often directly adjacent to or even atop these deterrents by kittiwakes, also demonstrates both the resilience of non-human spatial claims and the inherent limitations of purely exclusionary management strategies.

Moving forward, adopting MTH methods invites a shift from defensive design toward co-habitation frameworks that recognise buildings as potential multispecies habitats. Through spatial ethnography, material experimentation, and participatory design involving ecologists, residents, and non-human proxies, architects and planners can begin to reimagine façades, ledges, and rooftops as shared territories rather than conflict zones. Such approaches would not only accommodate ecological agency within the built environment but also foster more inclusive and resilient urban morphologies that support the coexistence of human and non-human life.

Conclusions

This study represents the first effort to compile a high-volume, multi-year dataset (2010–2025) on kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) within the cities of Newcastle and Gateshead in the UK, made available through an open-access framework. By integrating machine learning and GIS-based spatial analysis with a MTH theoretical lens, the research demonstrates that the presence and abundance of urban kittiwake colonies extend far beyond simple proximity to marine foraging areas. Instead, colony establishment and persistence emerge from complex interspecies negotiations mediated through urban morphology, a confluence of environmental factors including proximity to saltwater linked to marine food availability, urban structures that provide elevated ledges mimicking natural cliffside habitats, and reduced predation risk within the dense urban fabric (Redfern and Bevan, 2014; Coulson, 2011; Pais de Faria et al., 2021).

The finding reflects the species' pelagic ecology and specialist foraging behaviour, which depends exclusively on marine prey rather than terrestrial food sources. The preference for retail buildings and urban infrastructure such as bridges over vegetated areas shows how kittiwake habitat requirements differ fundamentally from those of most urban wildlife, reflecting their capacity to exploit specific morphological features of the built environment rather than conventional green infrastructure, and demonstrating their adaptability to urban environments. More significantly, from an MTH perspective, the spatial patterns revealed through this analysis expose how kittiwakes function as active urban agents that continuously negotiate and reshape urban space through their habitat choices and persistence despite exclusionary measures. It underscores the critical need to integrate interspecies requirements into conservation and urban planning strategies, ensuring that morphological and architectural prerequisites supporting multispecies coexistence are embedded within development frameworks.

While this study contributes to the literature by supporting ethnographic findings on kittiwake habitat use in urban areas through a data-led analysis, several limitations should be noted. First, although widely used analysis metrics (e.g. distance to water, percentage within land cover categories) were applied to evaluate environmental indicators of kittiwake abundance, these remain relatively coarse. Further research quantifying microclimatic heterogeneity across urban sites, such as wind velocity and shading patterns in conjunction with spatially explicit measures of human disturbance, may elucidate the fine-grained environmental thresholds influencing habitat selection decisions. Second, although certain key non-negotiable environmental determinants of kittiwake urban colonisation (e.g. proximity to water) were included, others were missing. For example, urban street network layout could be used as a proxy for pedestrian distribution and thus human disturbance. Third, architectural parameters beyond environmental factors and deterrence measurements were preliminary

considered, despite their likely importance for habitat selection. Future research at finer spatial scales—such as examining the presence of deterrents (e.g. spikes, nettings, etc.) or the width of ledges along riverside buildings—would help clarify how specific morphological and environmental features shape kittiwake adaptation to urban environments. Finally, the sample data analysed in this study were aggregated over a 15-year period. To better understand how habitat use varies in parallel with changes in urban morphology, future work should examine the temporal data at a more disaggregated scale (e.g. in 5-year intervals).

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